

Original Article

“Ratio of Gender Dependency”, A Comparative Study between Karachi and Hyderabad’s Populace

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ABSTRACT

Objective Karachi and Hyderabad both are metropolitan cities of Pakistan but Karachi is more developed and mobilized city than Hyderabad. This difference may possibly bring change in the gender dependency ratio. **Introduction** Gender is the socially and culturally shaped characteristics for males and females (sexes) of any society; both genders have to perform the roles which are expected from them. Gender dependency is the result of the cultural practices in any society while the culture in developing societies is masculine by its nature and men are the one who lead, secure and are responsible for bread earning for their families. **Methodology** To confirm this fact, data from 500 respondents was collected from Karachi and Hyderabad, age between 25 to 40 years. Questions about respondent’s experience, hesitation, insecurity, independency in decision making were also the part of detail questionnaire. **Results** this study shows that the ratio of educated population was high in Hyderabad. In both cities females were more dependent than males, Females of Karachi were more confident and independent in their lives and the level of insecurity was high in females of Hyderabad. **Conclusion** Findings proposed the importance of education, development and mobility on the road to independent life.

KEYWORDS

Gender Dependency, Hesitation, Insecurity, Decision Making, Mobility.

INTRODUCTION

Gender dependency is a common phrase that from childhood, people get to listen this word within their surroundings that one gender always lead and the other one follows (Ridgeway, 2004). The biological differentiation of characteristics one gets as being male or female is gender (Holmes, 2004). In every society each individual is gendered; so that they lie in one category of gender to play the part which is expected from them. This individual role and this categorization is significant in social life of any particular society (Wharton, 2009). This gender classification affects a lot on the way people behave towards any gender. These attitudes towards any gender can be a major contribution towards gender dependency and as it is believed that female gender is more dependent than male (Alonso, 2002).

Women in developing countries like Pakistan make decisions, that are not independent and self-sufficient for all society concerns, and they need to go for aid and assistance (Bryan, 2008). On the other side of the story the situation is slightly different in developed countries and the ratio of female gender dependency because genders are more equal in these societies where the value of labor for both genders is similar. Pakistan is a country where women are the leading one when it comes to the gender dependency, and they strictly face restrictions and limitations (Papanek, 1971).

In Pakistan the ratio of working men is higher than the ratio of working women (Ray, 2002), because women play important part in family; they are considered pillar of family and the most important component of the primary institution of society. Serious gender inequalities and human rights violation against women is present in Pakistan and women face serious restriction and limitations of autonomy (House, 2013). Rigid cultural norms are the major factor for conflict in ideas and practices in girls education (Flax, 1981; Greenspan, 1983; Litwin, 1986).

In past few years women literacy rate and their participation in economic activities have increased due to globalization but the quality of work condition and change in position and status of women needs consideration (Nasreen, 2012). The socio-economic condition of Pakistan is a major cause of female illiteracy (Memon, 2002) and education in this region do not offer better conditions due to religious constraints (Jayaweera, 1997), Studies have proved that financially dependent females are considered more powerless than (Ali, 2011).

Education enables to impact many discriminatory patterns (Malik, 2011). Majority of women in Pakistan obtain religious education and primary education (Razi, 2001), while the ratio of parents is increasing who want professional and occupational education for their daughters (Urooj, 2006).

METHODOLOGY

Cross-sectional observational study was carried from July 2013 to December 2014 on a designed questionnaire to evidence the demographic data & generalized question regarding gender dependency. Informed consent were obtained before the collection of data. Both male and female gender aged between 25- 40 were recruited without any biasness & the data was collected from 500 respondents (250 from Karachi and 250 from Hyderabad). SPSS version 21.0 was utilized for the statistical treatment of the data.

RESULTS

Findings showed that citizens of Karachi are more confident and independent in their lives. The level of insecurity was high in females of Hyderabad but the ratio of females who are dependent in decision making process was little high in Hyderabad; they take their decisions without any social pressure; due to the respondent’s high level of education as compare to females of Karachi. Majority of females from Karachi do not feel helpless without opposite gender due to mobility.

Fig 1: Results are showing low level of independency in females of Hyderabad in managing things outside home with 38.33% where as females of Karachi showed higher level of independency with 46.72.

Fig 4: Due to low level of education in respondents the ratio of insecurity is high in females of Karachi.

Fig 2: Males and females of Karachi showed almost same level of confidence in interacting with unknown people but in Hyderabad females showed high level of hesitation as compare to males in Hyderabad.

Fig 5: Ratio of females who feel helpless without opposite gender is high in Karachi with 51.85 as compare to females of Hyderabad with 50.57.

Fig 3: As ratio of literate female respondents was large in Hyderabad; females of Hyderabad showed higher level of independency in decision making as compare to the females of Karachi.

CONCLUSION

This study proposed the importance of education, development and mobility on the way to independent life. Education is an important element of women empowerment, but only education is not sufficient; Self-sufficiency here proved to be the major factor to be independent enough when it comes to decisions about oneself.

DISCUSSION

Women low self-esteem and poor confidence are few reasons which hinder the process of social change (Hazarika, 2012); and this is the dilemma in Asian society's culture that a good woman is characterized as empathetic, unselfish, tolerant, compromising and keeping good relationship, more over good women are also expected to hide their emotions and to compromise with their opinion for the sake of family's honor (Ali, 2011). Society's actions and practices are guided by the institutions and social group (Wharton, 2009); structure of these institutions varies from society to society. In Asian societies men are the primary authorities and women are their subordinates (Morrison, 2005). Girls watch their mothers being dependent, from childhood daughters grow up watching their mother sacrificing for every person of the family; she never even realized about her desires, this pattern of socialization turn off the self actualization mood of women and they stop thinking about themselves, and daughters

perceived themselves as their mothers (Boyd, 1987); mothers' role is very important in molding their daughters' personalities. Increase in education and cultural drift due to globalization have made the situation little favorable (Nasreen, 2012); because education is the tool which can make people competent enough to analyze, search and work for better conditions for themselves (Malik, 2011), but the main hindrance behind female gender dependency in developing countries is their less economic participation due to many social, cultural, economic and religious factors and people's stereotype about women's economic independency. Financially dependent housewives are considered having less power and authority (Gillespie, 1971). In majority cases women have no intensions or desires for independency or about self-actualization; they get higher education for getting good mates for marriage, not for their career or professional life (Hazarika, 2012).

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

Authors declare no conflict of interest.

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